

Hybrid robotic control for flexible element disassembly

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Abstract. This work proposes a robotic arm control for the disassembly of flexible elements. With this, a control solution is sought for handling paths of flexible elements where the application of an adequate force is necessary to ensure the physical integrity of the element. The proposal consists of an hybrid scheme to control the interaction between the robot end-effector and its environment, where the use of a global and a local planner helps to adapt a theoretical trajectory with real-time information during the execution of the task. The proposed control is implemented in a simulated environment on the robotic arms Franka Emika and KUKA LBR iiwa, resulting in trajectories that reduce the force in the flexible element.

Keywords: hybrid control, robot manipulation, robotic disassembly

1 Introduction

Robotics present a flexible and affordable solution for many industrial cases. In some of them is important the control of the interaction between the robot end-effector and its environment. To meet the requirements set by that interaction, it is necessary to control both force and position [1]. However, it is not straightforward since position and force are dependent control spaces. For that reason, the use of classic position and force controllers is not suitable for these tasks.

To accomplish with that interaction requirements, compliant control methodologies are used in robotic arms [2]. The differences between them lie mainly in the determination of the interaction forces, and in how different types of feedback signals are incorporated to achieve both force and position control to guarantee the desired interaction. Impedance controllers [3] and hybrid controllers [4] are the most commonly used methodologies for the control of robotic interaction tasks. In the former, the establishment of a relationship between position and force generates a mass-spring-damper behavior. On the other hand, in hybrid controllers, position and force control work in parallel, thus generating orthogonal control spaces.

Since these controllers are usually used in unstructured and dynamic tasks, main challenges are related to the significant work of design and adjustment of

Fig. 1. Fridge flexible element disassembly task.

the parameters that guarantee the desired interaction. To Face them, this work proposes an hybrid robotic control for flexible elements disassembly. This control generates manipulation trajectories guaranteeing the application of an adequate force on the manipulated element.

2 Flexible element disassembly

Disassembly of flexible elements expose many of the challenges discussed in the previous section and is present in several industrial fields, in which we can highlight the disassembly and reuse of flexible elements used for sealing doors of household appliances, automobiles, among other devices. In them is necessary the control of the interaction between the robot end-effector and the flexible element in order to guarantee both the execution of the task and to safeguard the physical integrity of the element.

An important aspect in these are the interaction forces that appear during the execution of the task, which are dynamic and vary according to the state and characteristics of the specific flexible element being manipulated. These forces influence the development of the task, so it is necessary to be able to identify them to achieve the correct interaction control. This characteristic, where the robot must be able to identify the forces and act according to them, causes that nowadays these types of tasks are performed manually. Nonetheless, the repetitive and in some cases non-ergonomic characteristics of these tasks can be harmful to people. For that reason this work proposes a robotic system solution capable of carrying out this type of tasks.

In Fig. 1, it can be observed the task of removing one of these elements in the door of a refrigerator. In this task, the flexible element must be detached from the door frame ensuring its physical integrity for future reuse. Thus, the objective of the task is to execute a removal trajectory that ensures the application of adequate force to the flexible element. Both trajectory planning and force

exertion present a challenge due to the different conditions that arise between different cases, where different extraction paths and force exertions are suitable.

Fig. 2. Hybrid control scheme proposal with the use of hybrid-planning framework

2.1 Hybrid force control strategy

For the challenges of flexible element manipulation, an hybrid force control is proposed based on the establishment of a reference trajectory that is modified by a force controller taking into account the interaction information of the system at runtime (green and blue trajectories in Fig.3.)

The proposed control is developed on the ROS2 framework. This framework aims to improve the performance offered by other frameworks based on the "sense-plan-act" methodology, that are inadequate for tasks where the environment and requirements change dynamically during execution. This is because in interaction tasks, the environment may have changed from planning to execution. For this reason, it is necessary to migrate to methodologies where the action is linked to the sensing in real-time.

This framework addresses this problem through the use of global and local planners. These components have different functions and operate at different fre-

quencies. In the case of the global planner, it is responsible for solving the global problem where there are no real-time requirements (theoretical trajectory). On the other hand, the local planner is responsible for adapting the solution of the global planner taking into account real-time information (interaction forces) about the environment.

The implementation of the control proposal using the hybrid planning framework is shown in Fig. 2. Where the theoretical trajectory is generated by the global planner using the Open Motion Planning Library (OMPL) [5]. This trajectory is made up by consecutive waypoints where the local planner works. It looks for the following waypoint and calculates the interaction force in that point, and with a proportional force action adapts it. Finally, the local planner executes the movement to the deviated position and repeats this action through the entire trajectory.

To coordinate the calls to the global and local planners, the manager logic in this work consists of calling the global planner at the beginning of the task to generate the theoretical reference trajectory. The local planner is then responsible for determining the forces acting on the task to modify this trajectory and send it to the robot for execution.

3 Results

The proposed control is implemented on the robotic arms Franka Emika and KUKA LBR iiwa, resulting in the trajectories shown in Figure 3. To generate the reference trajectories, an arbitrary starting point was established (yellow point), which corresponds to the point where the flexible element is held by the support. The end position of the trajectory (red point) was chosen to replicate real-world applications. For the Franka Emika robot (see Fig. 3(a)), no planner requirements are specified. However, for the KUKA iiwa robot (see Fig. 3(b)), the planner is required to generate Cartesian trajectories. This approach allows for the evaluation of the proposal with different types of trajectories.

The green trajectories generated by the global planner represent theoretical extraction trajectories, but they do not consider the interaction forces present during execution. As the robot motion begins, the local planner calculate the force present and adjusts the trajectory accordingly. At this stage, the forces are generated in simulation assuming that the element follows a Hooke's law model (considering grasping point as the equilibrium position and a elasticity constant of 100 N/m). The red arrows represent the proportional action of the force control that modifies the trajectory. Finally the robot send the modified trajectory (blue trajectory) for execution. This trajectory removes the flexible element while safeguarding its integrity.

4 conclusions

This paper presents the implementation of a robotic control system for the disassembly of flexible elements. An hybrid control approach is proposed to adapt

Fig. 3. simulation results of the proposed control strategy

trajectories according to the interaction forces present during execution, with the use of the ROS2 hybrid-planning framework.

The resulting trajectories are smooth and continuous, making them suitable for the manipulation of flexible elements. The use of the global planner enables the specification of reference trajectories at the beginning of the task, and then with the local planner real-time information about the forces during the execution are incorporated to take force control actions and modified the trajectory to one in which less force is exerted on the flexible element.

The proposal was implemented in a simulation environment to evaluate the use of the hybrid-planning framework. The next step of this proposal is to implement it in the real world and work with the KUKA lbr iiwa robot. This will allow for the use of real-time force data obtained through the robot sensors.

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References

1. P. Song, Y. Yu, and X. Zhang, “A tutorial survey and comparison of impedance control on robotic manipulation,” *Robotica*, vol. 37, pp. 801–836, 5 2019.
2. D. E. Whitney, “Historical perspective and state of the art in robot force control,” *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 3–14, 1987.
3. N. Hogan, “Impedance control: An approach to manipulation,” in *1984 American control conference*. IEEE, 1984, pp. 304–313.
4. M. T. Mason, “Compliance and force control for computer controlled manipulators,” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, vol. 11, pp. 418–432, 1981.
5. I. A. Şucan, M. Moll, and L. E. Kavraki, “The Open Motion Planning Library,” *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 72–82, December 2012.